

ANALYSIS OF THE COATING STOKESIAN FLOW

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ABSTRACT

The coating is an important industrial process, which creates a thin layer of dispersion, solution or liquid monomer that is then solidified by drying, curing etc. There are two main configurations of the process, vertical and horizontal. This paper deals with the vertical orientation. The entire domain is considered and separated into three regions. Solutions are obtained to various zones and then stitched to solve for the entire fluid field. In this process the asymptotic technique is used to take advantage of the character and behavior of each region so that the total solution can be obtained. The core of this analysis potentially could be utilized with other methods. Comparison with experimental works are in fairly good agreement.

NOMENCLATURE

a Film thickness
 E Deviation of the free surface
 g Gravitational acceleration constant
 p Pressure
 P_m Integration constant
 R Radius of the curvature
 T Capillary number
 U Speed at $x = 0$
 x Coordinate
 y Coordinate
Greek Letters

ν kinematic viscosity
 β Integration constant
 δ Small distance
 γ Angle between the free surface and η
 ε Small parameter
 η Coordinate in complex plane
 ξ Coordinate in complex plane
 ψ Stream function
 $\bar{\psi}$ Stream function at the free surface
 ρ Liquid density
 τ_{ns} Shear stress at the surface
 τ_{nn} “Pressure” stress at the surface

Key Words

Vertical Coating flow, Small Reynolds number, Perturbation methods, Connecting different regions solved separately.

1 Introduction

The coating process is considered to be a two dimensional process in which liquid (or semi-solid or powder) is sprayed on or coating a flat (or circular) solid body, and the layer is dried (e.g., solidified, or cured) (Bar-Meir 2021a). The coating process can be continuous or sprayed (as powder or drop) vertical or horizontal. All these coating processes have benefits and drawbacks. The continuous vertical is the least energy demanding (in some sense like no pump is required). However, this technology suffers from a lack of theoretical relationship between the coat thickness and operational parameters, and in fact, trial and error is required

*The author to whom correspondence should be addressed. However, please note that this paper resulted from a work conducted by Prof. M. Bentwich during the late 1980’s and the corresponding author has extremely small roll in conceiving the underlying ideas.

to connect the coat thickness to the belt speed and fluid properties.

While there are situations where after hundreds of teams and many years attempting to solve a problem like the plunger critical velocity in die casting, a simple solution appeared from nowhere (Bar-Meir and Brauner 2021) or boiling (Zuber 1958). Another case is the solution for oblique shock (Bar-Meir 2021b) appearing from nowhere. Here, simple solution does not likely to appear and in fact, the trail and error is required to connect the coat thickness with to the belt speed and the liquid properties.

The vertical coating process is similar to the dipping process. In both processes the dominant force is the surface tension which is at molecular scale. Admittedly, this paper deals with low Reynolds number flow yet at very low velocity the nature of the flow change from 2-dimensional flow to 3-dimensional flow. Below a certain limit, the flow is far from 2-dimensional. For example, when rain hits the windshield, the water streams in streaks and is not continuous¹ hence this analysis is not applicable. This paper does not offer a discussion on this point.

The flow depicted in fig. 1 is idealized for that taking place in a standard vertical coating process. The plane $x=0$ represents one of the right surfaces of a belt. Such a belt is dipped in a bath full of liquid (molten) coating material, which is kept at this state by heating (or other methods). As the belt is pulled upwards it drags certain amount of liquid, which forms a uniform layer high up. When this layer is exposed to the atmosphere it cools (etc) and forms a coat of constant thickness. Of course, the thickness is not uniform close to the edge of the plate, or wherever the vertical planes bounding the object meet at an angle. The situation at the vicinity of such corners has been analyzed by Tuck, Bentwich and Van der Hoek (1983) who assumed that the flow is purely vertical, and indeed it is at high up. This work attention is focused on the drawing mechanism and the actual formation of the vertical flowing layer. Thus, the flow in the entire two dimensional domain shown in the fig. 1 is analyzed by accounting for the effects of the gravity, surface tension and viscosity.

The ultimate width of the fluid layer a , is related by a very simple formula to $\bar{\psi}$, the upward volumetric flow rate (per unit plane's breadth). The width of the coat, once it becomes solid, is obviously $\bar{\psi}/a$. The design of the coating processes can be controlled by varying the belt speed (withdrawal velocity) or modifying liquid properties like the surface tension by adding surfactant for example. Hence

¹Some of the discussion here is taken from Laurence Edward "Skip" Scriven coating flow classes in chemical engineering in Minnesota in 1998–1999 which the second author attended. Another part is from the experiments carried by the second author in Tel-Aviv university [doi:10.5281/zenodo.6049814](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6049814) were not published.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of belt moving up and liquid “coats” belt

most of the analytical and experimental investigations of the problem at hand many were reported/culminate in a graph or table representing the ultimate width as function of the capillary number. So does the analysis proposed (Spiers, Subbaraman, and Wilkinson 1974).

Broadly speaking, one can recognize in the flow under discussion three regimes of three distinctly different characters. There is the layer adjacent to the vertical plane, throughout which the flow is more or less vertical. Next to it there is central region where the streamline $\psi = -\bar{\psi}$ (see fig. 1), which emanates deep in the bath, splits at the free surface and thus forms two branches. One curves upwards while the other becomes horizontal. The third region is that prevailing in the tub where the flow is rather slow and the free surface is more or less flat, because there gravity dominates over all the other fluid mechanics effects. Now it is obviously difficult to account for everything that happens in all three regimes. Furthermore, it was often thought that, in order to attain the prime target, this is not necessary. Thus, numerous attempts were made to evaluate a , by analyzing just a portion of the flow domain. In their pioneering work, Landau and Levich (1988) do so by focusing on the central region. In subsequent works their treatment was refined. In many other articles it is the vertically flowing layer which is analyzed, assuming that the velocity distribution at the entry to be known.

What has been obviously lacking (see the comprehensive and up to date list of references compiled by Spiers, Subbaraman and Wilkinson (1974), is an analysis of the entire flow domain shown in the fig. 1. This is done herewith by obtaining solution of the Stokes equation in this domain. It satisfies the well known boundary conditions on both the solid and the free surface, when the position of the latter is unknown. In the course of its construction certain

mathematical approximations are made. But the impact of the latter can be readily examined and assessed. Consequently, although, when judged from a physical viewpoint, the solution proposed is inexact, because inertia is ignored, the elliptic nature of the problem is fully accounted for. To the best of the authors' knowledge so far this has not been achieved, although a big stride towards that aim has been recently made by Wilson (1982). Indeed, his solution accounts for the flow in the layer and central region but not the tub.

Since there are distinct regimes, and yet one would like to account for the patently elliptic nature of the flow problems, the latter is approached as follows. Three regional approximate solutions are constructed in the form of asymptotic expansions, which are determinable to within free constants, of which a (or $\bar{\psi}$) is just one. Then every pair of expansions, which constitute approximate solutions in adjacent domains, is matched. Thus, the free constants are evaluated and the construction of the solution, converting the entire domain, is completed.

Over the last three decades the so called “matching and patching” approach, which is described above, was applied in almost every branch of fluid mechanics. However, it seems that it is just one version of this approach that was widely used, namely that which hinges on the smallness, or else the largeness, of the characteristic parameter of the problem which is to be solved. Typical examples of the uses of that version are the analyses of high and low Reynolds number flows past obstacles. But the problem under discussion is not characterized by such parameter, and hence, at first glance, it appears insolvable by the approach under the discussion. Indeed, the flow at hand is defined in term of just one parameter, the capillary number T^{-1} . Yet, it has only marginal influence on the flow investigated here (see the a vs. T^{-1} curve in fig. 3. It therefore, cannot play an analogous role to the played by Reynolds number in the analyses of the flows past obstacles. Anyway, one would like to obtain a solution which holds for a wide range of T , rather than for the limiting cases in which this parameter is either very large or else vanishing small.

Fortunately, as in a similar situation here too the absence of a natural small, or large, parameter can be circumvented by introducing one. Consequently the standard version of the matching procedure is applicable here. It is shown here that it is not necessary to adhere to that version, and that the “matching and patching” approach is also applicable to problems which are not characterized by small parameter.

FIGURE 2. The complex plane

2 Formulation of the Problem

With $\sqrt{\nu U/g}$ as the characteristic length, and when the stream function and the pressure are normalized with respect to $\sqrt{\nu U/g}$ and $\rho \sqrt{\nu U/g}$, respectively, and governing equation read

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right) (p + y) = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right) \nabla^2 \psi \quad (1)$$

Here ρ is the liquid density ν is the kinematic viscosity g is the gravitational acceleration while U is the speed at which the plane $x = 0$ is pulled upwards. Accordingly, the conditions imposed on that surface are

$$\begin{cases} \psi = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = -1 \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} x = 0 \\ -\infty < y < \infty \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

On the free surface the following conditions are imposed

$$\psi = -\bar{\psi} \quad (3)$$

$$\tau_{ns} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_{nm} = -\frac{T}{R} \quad (5)$$

The first of these reflects that fact that surface constitutes a streamline. Conditions eq. (4) is zero shear at the free surface and eq. (5) is the pressure condition. The right hand side of the latter represent the effect of the surface tension, τ because R is the local normal radius of the curvature while T is the normalized surface tension $\tau/\rho \nu U$. Thus, as stated, in this problem T , which equal to inverse of the capillary number, is the only physical parameter.

This formulation is in terms of the three dependent variables. Of these the stream function, ψ and pressure p appear explicitly in eq. (1) and eq. (2), obtain the bihar-

monic equation

$$\nabla^4 \psi = 0 \quad (6)$$

and get a solution of ψ , such process will serve just as an intermediate step. To complete the analysis one must keep track of p so that condition eq. (5) can be met. The third dependent variable is introduced below and it defines the geometry of the free surface. The existence of this unknown is also reflected in the formulation, where only two conditions are imposed on the solid plane while three on the free surface.

It is difficult to solve this set of equations in the domain under discussion, namely that shown in fig. 1. Therefore, a conformal transformation is made

$$iz = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} (\xi + \exp(\xi)) \right) \quad (7)$$

which maps the physical domain onto a more manageable one. The bottom line $\eta = 0$, of the strip $0 < \eta < \pi/2$ $-\infty < \xi < \infty$, (shown in fig 2) maps onto the solid surface $x = 0$. The other boundary of the strip, $\eta = \pi/2$, maps onto a curve in the z plane which is hopefully close to the free surface. It approaches the vertical section $x = a$ at the $\xi \sim -\infty$ end, while at the other end it is roughly given by

$$x \sim \frac{2a}{\pi} \exp(\xi) \quad y \sim -\frac{2a}{\pi} \xi \quad (8)$$

Therefore, its downward slope becomes extremely small as ξ is increased. It follows that one can hope to represent the free surface by

$$\eta = \frac{\pi}{2} + E(\xi) \quad (9)$$

Accordingly, the third unknown is E , and it represents the deviation of the free surface from the line $\eta = \pi/2$ in the ξ plane. It is assumed that this quantity not only decays for $\xi \sim \pm\infty$ but is also small in between, so that perturbation techniques can be used in processing conditions (4) and (5). The results obtained are compatible with this assumption.

Recasting equations eq. (1)–(5) in terms of (ξ, η) one gets

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \right) (p+y) = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi}, -\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \right) \frac{\nabla^2 \psi}{h^2} \quad (10)$$

where here the Laplacian is in (ξ, η) and h^2 is given by

$$h^2 = \left| \frac{dz}{d\xi} \right| = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right)^2 \left(1 + 2 \cos(\eta) e^\xi + e^{2\xi} \right) \quad (11)$$

The boundary conditions reads

$$\psi = 0, \quad \eta = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} = \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) (1 + e^\xi) \quad \eta = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\psi = -\psi \quad \eta = \pi/2 + E \quad (14)$$

$$\tau_{\xi\eta} \cos(2\gamma) - \tau_{\xi\xi} \sin(2\gamma) = 0 \quad \eta = \pi/2 + E \quad (15)$$

$$-p - \tau_{\xi\eta} \sin(2\gamma) - \tau_{\xi\xi} \cos(2\gamma) = \frac{T}{R} \quad \eta = \pi/2 + E \quad (16)$$

Here γ is the angle between the free surface and the $\eta = \text{const.}$ curve and can therefore be evaluated in terms of $E(\xi)$. So can the radius of curvature R . The components of extra stress which appear in equations (15) and (16) are related to the stream function via

$$\frac{1}{2} \overline{\tau_{\xi\xi}} = -\frac{\overline{\tau_{\eta\eta}}}{2} = \frac{1}{h^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} - \frac{1}{h^3} \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \eta} \right] \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \overline{\tau_{\xi\eta}} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \eta^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \xi^2} \right) - \frac{2}{h^3} \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \xi} \right] \quad (18)$$

3 Regional Solution for the Layer

For large $(-\xi)$ the following approximation is expected to hold

$$\left(\frac{2a}{h\pi} \right)^2 \sim 1 - 2 \cos(\eta) e^\xi + (2 \cos(2\eta) + 1) e^{2\xi} + 0 \left(e^{3\xi} \right) \quad \xi \sim -\infty \quad (19)$$

Accordingly, the dependent variable are expressed as follows

$$\psi \sim G_0(\eta) + G_1(\eta) e^\xi + 0(e^{2\xi}) \quad \xi \sim -\infty \quad (20)$$

$$(p+y) \sim p_0(\eta) + p_1(\eta) e^\xi + 0(e^{2\xi}) \quad \xi \sim -\infty \quad (21)$$

$$E \sim E_1(\eta) e^\xi + 0(e^{2\xi}) \quad \xi \sim -\infty \quad (22)$$

This form of solution is evidently incomplete. But in order to explain in what sense it is lacking, the analysis will be pursued assuming that it holds. Thus, substituting from

relationships eq. (19) and eq. (20) into the following form of the governing equations,

$$\nabla^2 \left(\frac{1}{h^2} \right) \nabla^2 \psi = 0 \quad (23)$$

where in this relationship the Laplacian is in (ξ, η) , one finds that G_0 is governed by

$$\frac{d^4 G_0}{d\eta^4} = 0 \quad (24)$$

The solution for G_0 must also satisfy the boundary condition (12) and (13), where on the right hand side of the latter the term of the $0(e^\xi)$ is suppressed, and it is given by:

$$G_0 = \frac{2a\eta}{\pi} + \frac{a^3}{6} \left[3 \left(\frac{2\eta}{\pi} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{2\eta}{\pi} \right)^3 \right] \quad (25)$$

It follows from the Cauchy–Riemann relations (23) that the leading component of $(p+y)$ is

$$p+y \sim - \left(\frac{2a\xi}{\pi} \right) \quad (26)$$

so that if the free surface coincides with $\eta = \pi/2$, γ vanishes and the solution eq. (25) satisfies condition (15) and (16). Condition (5') then yields the well known interdependence

$$\bar{\psi} = a - \frac{a^3}{3} \quad (27)$$

Linking the volumetric flow rate with the width of the layer. Indeed, high up on the plane $(-\psi)$ is very large and (x,y) are approximately equal to $(2/a/\pi)(\eta, -\xi)$. Therefore, the results obtained verify that the flow there is purely vertical.

The next step is to obtain the refinement of $0(e^\xi)$. Retaining in relationship (60) and (20) two terms, the bi-harmonic equation (23) reduces to

$$\nabla^2 \left\{ \left[G_0'' + e^\xi \left(\frac{d^2}{d\xi^2} + 1 \right) G_1 \right] (1 - 2 \cos(\eta) e^\xi) \right\} = 0 \quad (28)$$

When the terms of $0(e^0)$ are equated to zero one recovers equation (24) which has been satisfied. Equating the terms

of $0(e^0)$ to zero one gets

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{d\xi^2} + 1 \right)^2 G_1 = a^3 \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{2\eta}{\pi} \right) \cos(\eta) \quad (29)$$

Solving the latter and invoking the two conditions imposed over the solid boundary, with the term of $0(e)$ in (13) included, one gets

$$G_1 = - \left(\frac{2a \sin(\eta)}{\pi} \right) - \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\eta^2 \sin(\eta)}{2} \right) + B_1 (\eta \cos(\eta) - \sin(\eta)) + C_1 \left(\frac{2\eta \sin(\eta)}{\pi} \right) \quad (30)$$

From the Cauchy–Riemann equation (23) one gets

$$p_1 = - \left(2B_1 + \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right)^3 \right) \cos(\eta) + 2 \left(a^3 \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right)^2 - C_1 \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) \right) \sin(\eta) \quad (31)$$

Thus the refinement of the $0(e^\xi)$ which meets conditions (12) and (13) is in terms of three constraints B_1 , C_1 , and E_1 . Relationships governing these are obtained by imposing the remaining three free–surface conditions. As pointed out, this is done by perturbing around $\eta = \pi/2$. Since this process is repeated in the course of this work it will be explained in detail only once using the step under discussion as an example.

Condition (14) is written as follows

$$\frac{G_0 \pi}{2} + \frac{G_0' \pi E_1 e^\xi}{2} + \frac{G_1 \pi E_1 e^\xi}{2} = -\bar{\psi} \quad (32)$$

where terms of the higher order are suppressed. The term $G_0'(\pi/2)E_1 e^\xi$, which is the second component in the Taylor expansion around $\eta = \pi/2$, is retained, while the third component $G_0''(\pi/2)(1/2)E_1^2 e^{2\xi}$ and the higher ones are neglected. Now the terms of $0(e^0)$ were balanced in the course of the solution of $G_0(\eta)$. The balancing of the terms of $0(e^0)$ yields equation eq. (32) (see below), which is one of the three relationships required to determine the refinement of the that order. The processing of the equation (15) and (16) provides the other two. The angle γ which appears in these is $\tan^{-1}(E'(\xi))$ and it follows from the form (22)

that it is of $O(e^\xi)$. Therefore, the cosines in conditions (15) and (16) are approximately equal to unity and the sines are of $O(e^\xi)$. But from equations (18), (18), (21) and (25) one gathers that the stresses are at most of $O(e^\xi)$. Hence at this state of the analysis it is only products of these times $\cos(2\gamma)$, which is unity, that have to be taken into account.

Thus, as explained above equation yields

$$(E_1 - 1) \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{\pi} \right) + B_1 - C_1 = -\frac{2a^3}{\pi} \quad (33)$$

Equation (6') provides the relationship

$$(E_1 + 1) \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right)^3 + 2C_1 = 2 \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) a^3 \quad (34)$$

to which the solution $G_0(\eta)$ contributes two components. One is due to the evaluation of the term $1/h^2(\partial^2\psi/\partial\eta^2)$ of relationship (18) at $\eta = \pi/2 + E$, rather than on $\eta = \pi/2$. The second contribution is due to the term $(\partial h/\partial\eta)(\partial\psi/\partial\eta)$ in that relationship. Finally, by similarly processing the stress term $\tau_{\xi\xi}$ and approximating $1/R$ by $E''(\xi)/h^2$ one finds that conditions (16) yields

$$(E_1 + 1) \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) \left(\frac{2T}{\pi} \right) - 2B_1 = 0 \quad (35)$$

Solving for $(B_1 - C_1)$ from the latter two and substituting the results in equation (33) one gets

$$(E_1 + 1) \left\{ (2 - a^2) + \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{2T}{\pi} \right) \right\} = 0 \quad (36)$$

There are obviously two ways to satisfy this relationship. One can equate the expression in the curly brackets to zero and get an equation linking a with T . Such result must be ruled out because, as has been argued all along, the problem at hand is elliptic so that a and $\bar{\psi}$, cannot be determined by considering only the layer region. It follows that the only acceptable solution of the equations (33), (34) and (35) is that for which the expression in the first set of brackets vanishes. In such case the constants are given by

$$E_1 = -1 \quad B_1 = 0 \quad C_1 = \frac{2a^3}{\pi} \quad (37)$$

This results is correct, but it suggests that there is

something missing in the form (20)–(22). Firstly, because the result eq. (37) leaves the free surface straight and vertical, for its position is given by:

$$x \sim \frac{2a}{\pi} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} + E_1 e^\xi + e^\xi \right) \quad (38)$$

Secondly, because the term of $O(e^\xi)$ that was calculated is determinable without considering the flow in the adjacent central region. Moreover, it seems that so are all higher order terms in the form, which are of $O(e^{n\xi})$ where n is an integer.

The inadequacy of the form (20)–(22) becomes apparent when one observes that the factor e^ξ fits the analysis which is based on the mapping (7). But clearly the latter has nothing to do with the physical mechanism which governs the tapering of the layer as one proceeds upwards. Since that mechanism has to be accounted for one must add to the form (20)–(22) a perturbation term which varies like $e^{\delta\xi}$ where δ is an unknown. Evidently such perturbation is an eigensolution of the differential system governing the flow at $\xi \sim -\infty$. It corresponds to the eigenvalue δ , which represents the manner in which the layer becomes thinner. The amplitude of this eigensolution is unknown, so that if it is added to the form (20)–(22) the latter becomes determinable to within a free constant.

Therefore the following revised form of the solution is assumed

$$\psi \sim G_0(\eta) + G_1(\eta)e^\xi + \hat{G}(\eta)e^{\delta\xi} \quad \xi \sim -\infty \quad (39)$$

$$ip + y \sim p_1(\eta)e^\xi + \hat{p}(\eta)e^{\xi\delta} \quad (40)$$

$$E \sim E_1 e^\xi + \hat{E}(\eta)e^{\xi\delta} \quad \xi \sim -\infty \quad (41)$$

Solving for \hat{G} one gets

$$\hat{G} = \hat{B}(\delta\eta \cos(\delta\eta) - \sin(\delta\eta)) + \hat{C}(\delta\eta) \sin(\delta\eta) \quad (42)$$

where this expression meets the two conditions imposed at $\eta = 0$. Using this, \hat{p} is obtained from the Cauchy–Riemann equations (23). Then, by invoking the free surface conditions, and noting that $(\hat{B}, \hat{C}, \text{and } \hat{E})$ play similar roles to

those played by $(B_1, C_1, \text{ and } E_1)$, one gets

$$-\frac{2a}{\pi} \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2}\right) \hat{E} + (t \cos(t) - \sin(t)) \hat{B} + t \sin(t) \hat{C} = 0 \quad (43)$$

$$a^2 \left(\frac{2a}{\pi}\right) \hat{E} - 2t^3 \cos(t) \hat{B} + 2t^2 (\cos(t) - t \sin(t)) \hat{C} = 0 \quad (44)$$

$$T \left(\frac{2a}{\pi}\right) \hat{E} - 2 (t \sin(t) + \cos(t)) \hat{B} + 2t \cos(t) \hat{C} = 0 \quad (45)$$

Of course the big difference between this set and (33)–(35) is the former is homogeneous. It follows that a non-trivial refinement of $0(e^{\delta\xi})$ cannot be included in the form (22)–(25) unless t , which is $(\delta\pi/2)$, is such that the determinant of the coefficients of equations (45)–(47) vanishes. Consequently, the eigenvalue δ is linked to a and T by

$$T (\cos(t) \cos(t) - t) - a^2 + (2 - a^2) (\cos^2(t) - t^2) = 0 \quad (46)$$

Naturally it is the eigenvalue with the lowest real part with is of interest. The corresponding eigensolution $(G, p, \text{ and } E)$ represents the perturbations in the stream function, the pressure and the geometry of the free surface, respectively, of the decaying disturbance superposed on the otherwise purely vertical flow. It is convenient to regard \hat{E} as its amplitude and determine \hat{B} and \hat{C} , which appear in the expressions for $\hat{G}(\eta)$ and $\hat{p}(\eta)$, in terms of that variable using equations (43) and (44). Note that the eigensolutions used here related to the well know ones that were developed by Papkovich (1940) and Fadle (1940) and have been widely used since (see discussion on the orthogonality of this kind of function in (Bentwich and Bar-Meir 2022)). Indeed, the product $G(\eta) \exp(\delta\xi)$ is biharmonic in (ξ, η) . Therefore \hat{G} and Papkovich–Fadle eigenfunctions satisfy the very same governing equation. The difference is in the boundary conditions. The Papkovich–Fadle eigenfunctions were developed in order to solve solid mechanics problems where the position of the boundary surfaces are fixed and known. In the problem at hand, the position of the boundary has to be determined, and evidently this difference has a profound influence on the nature of the solution. The eigenvalues of the Papkovich–Fadle series are all complex, so that the products representing biharmonic solutions oscillates in the ξ direction. However, so long as T is not too large, the eigenvalues of equation (46) with lowest real part has no imaginary component. Therefore, as one would expect, the width of the layer thins monotonically like $e^{\delta\xi}$, and eventually attain the value a as one proceeds upwards.

It is also found that for the above stated range of T the actual value of δ is much smaller than unity. This

necessitates a change in the mathematical formulation. Because with the perturbation procedure used, the term of $0(e^{\delta\xi})$ generates contributions of the $0(e^{n\delta\xi})$ where n runs over all integers for which $n\delta$ is smaller than unity. Rather than account for these the calculations are streamlined by suppressing also the terms of $0(e^{\xi})$ in the expansions (14)–(16').

4 Regional Solution for the Tub and Central Region

In view of the condition (13) the leading term in the solution of large ξ which presents the flow in the tube, is assume to be of the form

$$\psi \sim e^{\xi} F_1(\eta) \quad (47)$$

Approximating the factor h^2 as follows:

$$\left(\frac{2a}{\pi h}\right)^2 \sim e^{-2\xi} - e^{-3\xi} 2 \cos(\eta) + e^{-4\xi} (2 \cos(2\eta) + 1) \quad \xi \sim \infty \quad (48)$$

and substituting from the last two equations into (23) and neglecting terms of $0(e^{2\xi})$ and smaller one gets

$$\left(\frac{d^2}{d\eta^2} + 1\right)^2 F_1 = 0 \quad (49)$$

The solutions for F_1 is therefore given by

$$F_1 = -\left(\frac{2a}{\pi}\right) e^{\xi} \sin(\eta) \left(1 - \frac{2\eta}{\pi}\right) \quad (50)$$

and this satisfies not only the governing equation but also (12) and (13). Moreover, assuming tentatively that for $\xi \sim \infty$ E vanishes, one finds from conditions (14) and (15) that $F_1 \pi/2$ and $F_1''(\pi/2)$ must be zero and these requirements are satisfied by the solution for F_1 as given by eq. (50). Condition (16) is also met to within an error of $0(e^{\xi})$.

The corresponding expression for E is then obtained by taking the Laplacian of relationship eq. (50) and multiplying it by the approximate form eq. (48). Then, using the

Cauchy–Riemann equations (10), one gets

$$(p+y) \sim \frac{2a\beta}{\pi} + \left(\frac{2e^{-\xi}}{a}\right) \sin(\eta) \quad \xi \sim \infty \quad (51)$$

where β is a constant of integration. It follows that if the displacement of the free surface is given by

$$E \sim (\sim (\xi + \beta) e^{-\xi} \quad (52)$$

then that surface levels off at $y = (2a\beta)/\pi$ and the pressure along it decays like $(2/a)E^{-\xi}$.

The development of the refined expansion representing the flow in the tub is similar to that of the solution for the layer. It is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \sim & -\left(\frac{2a}{\pi}\right) e^{\xi} \sin(n) \left(1 - \frac{2\eta}{\pi}\right) - \left(\frac{2a\eta}{\pi}\right) + \\ & I [\xi (\cos(2\eta) - 1) + \eta \sin(2\eta)] + \frac{M}{\pi} (\sin(2\eta) - 2n) + \\ & N (\cos(2n) - 1) + \frac{a4\eta^2}{\pi^2} + \\ & \frac{J}{\pi} [\eta(\cos(2\eta) - 1) - \xi(\sin(2\eta) - 2\eta)] \quad (53) \end{aligned}$$

where I , J , M and N are constants. Indeed with $1/h^2$ given by relationship (48) ψ as given by relationship (47), is biharmonic to within an error of $0(e^{-3\xi})$. For example, the Laplacian of the leading term times the component $(-2e^{-3\xi} \cos(\eta))$ of relationship (48) plus the product of $a(2/\pi)^2 \eta^2$ times $e^{-2\xi}$ add up to a term which is harmonic in (ξ, η) . The term $(-2a/\pi)\eta$ is harmonic and therefore also biharmonic. Its η derivative at $\eta = 0$ together with that of the leading term add up to the right hand side of condition (13). The rest of expansion (53) is the most general expression for a distribution which satisfies three requirements. It is biharmonic to within the stated error. Secondly, in view of the conditions (12) and (13), it has vanishing zeroth as well as first derivatives on $\eta = 0$. Thirdly, for fixed η it is linear in ξ , so that with E given by relationship (52) it could meet the free surface conditions.

It was found that when the constants satisfy the following equations

$$J = 0 \quad I = \frac{a}{2} \left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^2 \quad \psi = M + 2N - \beta a \left(\frac{2}{\pi}\right)^2 \quad (54)$$

then conditions (14), (15), and (16) are satisfied to within errors of $0(\xi e^{-\xi})$, $0(e^{-\xi})$, and $0(e^{-\xi})$, respectively Unlike the solution for the layer, expansions (53) does not project a clear distinction between eigensolutions, which are multiplied free constants, on the one hand and components that are complementary determined on the other. but this is immaterial. What is important is that ψ , a , β , J , I , M and N are unknown so that in view of equation (27) and (54) the solution for the flow in the tub is determinable in terms of M , N , and β .

Finally, the solution for the central region is constructed. Unlike those for the outlying regions it is for more accurate at the $\eta = 0$ side of the strip. For it is based on the following expansions around the origin:

$$\left(\frac{2a}{\pi h}\right)^2 \sim \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \xi + \frac{\xi^2 + \eta^2}{4}\right) \quad \xi, \eta \sim 0 \quad (55)$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} \Big|_0 \sim \frac{4a}{\pi} \left(1 + \frac{\xi}{2} + \frac{\xi^2}{4} + \frac{\xi^3}{12}\right) \quad \xi, \eta \sim 0 \quad (56)$$

which lies on the vertical plane. Therefore, in its vicinity the solution for ψ , that is biharmonic and satisfies the conditions on the $\eta = 0$ to within and error of $0(\eta^p \xi^q)$, where $p+q = 3$, is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi \sim & \left(\frac{4a}{\pi}\right) \left\{ \eta + \frac{\xi \eta}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \left(\eta \xi^2 - \frac{\eta^3}{3}\right) + \right. \\ & \frac{1}{12} (\eta \xi^3 - \eta^3 \xi) K \left[\eta^2 + \xi \eta^2 + \frac{9\eta^2 \xi^2 - 2\eta^4}{12} \right] + \\ & S [(1 + \xi) \eta^3] + Q \xi \eta^3 + \\ & \left. R (3 \xi^3 \eta^2 - \eta^4) \right\} \quad \xi, \eta \sim 0 \quad (57) \end{aligned}$$

The associated pressure distribution is obtained, as explained, by integrating the Cauchy–Riemann equations in which use is made of there approximate relationship (55). One thus gets

$$(p+y) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\pi}{2a} \left\{ p_m - 2L\eta + 6S + 3Q(\xi^2 - \eta^2) - \right. \\ \left. 12R\xi\eta \right\} \quad \xi, \eta \sim 0 \quad (58)$$

where P_m , like β is equations (51), is a constant of integration.

The position of the free surface is assumed to be given

by the form

$$E \sim e_0 + e_1 \xi \quad (59)$$

Using conditions (14), (15) and (16) one could express L , S , Q , and R in terms of a , P_m , K , e_0 and e_1 so that the latter five can be assumed to constitute the free constant characterizing the solution at the central region. In principle, that operation relates the variable characterizing the geometry of the free surface with those representing the adjacent flow and pressure fields. But it does that badly because the solution for these fields, which are based on expanded around the origin, cannot be accepted to be accurate close to the free surface. Indeed, this is reflected by the inadequacy of the results for high capillary numbers, when the interplay between the various effects come to the surface are of significance.

5 Completion of the Solution

The solutions for the outlying regions were developed assuming that $+\xi$ and $-\xi$ are large. But one can replace the independent variables (ξ, η) by $(\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon, \eta)$ and assume instead that $(\hat{\xi}, \eta)$ are of the $O(1)$ and ε is vanishingly small. With this replacement relationships (19) and (48) become

$$\left(\frac{2a}{\pi h}\right)^2 \sim 1 - 2\cos(\eta)e^{\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon} - e^{-4\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon} \cos(\eta) \quad \varepsilon \sim 0 \quad (60)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{2a}{\pi h}\right)^2 \sim e^{-2\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon} - e^{-4\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon} \cos \eta \quad \varepsilon \sim 0 \quad (61)$$

Replacing, accordingly, the differential operator $(\partial/\partial\xi)$ by $(\partial/\partial\hat{\xi})$ and analyzing the flow fields in the outlying regions one recovers relationships (20)–(22) and (53), in which ξ is replaced by $\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon$. These new forms of solutions differ from the one ones in that they constitute asymptotic expansions for small ε rather than for large $|\xi|$. But this difference is just a matter of presentation. Both forms represent the flow solutions in the outlying regions, where the “axial” variations (in terms of the strip shown in Fig 2) are much weaker than variations in the “transverse” direction.

Again, replacing (ξ, η) by $\varepsilon'(\xi', \eta')$ and the operators $(\partial/\partial\xi, \partial/\partial\eta)$ by $1/\varepsilon'(\partial/\partial\xi', \partial/\partial\eta')$, where the ratio ε' is taken to be small, one recovers the results (57). Indeed, these replacements reflect the assumptions underlying

its development, i.e. that this solution is restricted to the vicinity of the origin and that its “axial” and the “transverse” variations are of the same order of magnitude.

Now, that the regional solutions, which are to be matched, are expressed as asymptotic expansions for small ε and ε' , the standard procedure can be employed (see References (Kaplun 1957)(Proudman and Pearson 1957)(Kevorkian and Cole 2013)). Accordingly, the expansion for the vicinity of the origin is rewritten in terms of $(\hat{\xi}, \eta)$. Its components are found to increase like powers of the form $(\hat{\xi}/\varepsilon)p(\eta/\varepsilon)$ as ε decreases while the errors in the solutions for the outlying regions are much smaller. They decay like $\exp(-|\xi|/\varepsilon)$. Therefore, following the texts, none of the components of the from (57) are suppressed. On the other hand when $(\hat{\xi}, \eta)$ are replaced by $(\varepsilon\xi', \varepsilon'\eta')$ in the solutions for the outlying region, these are expressible as expansions consisting of the terms of the type $(\varepsilon')^i (\varepsilon')^j$. But while i and j run over all integers, the form (57) contains just a few terms. Suppressing most and equating only those, which are of the $O((\varepsilon')^0(\varepsilon')^2)$ or smaller, one gets the following interrelationships between the free constants appearing in the solutions that were matched:

$$(a\pi) = \frac{a^3}{2} + Ct^2 \quad (62)$$

$$\frac{a^3}{2} + Ct^2 = 3a - 2N \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \quad (63)$$

In the foregoing the matching was carried out by converting the “coordinate based” asymptotic expansions, to “parameter based” ones. This course was taken here, and only once, because then the matching can be carried out by adopting the familiar “epsilon formalism.” However, it is algebraically easier and logically more straightforward to match the coordinate expansions as they are. Therefore, it is the latter course, which is equivalent to the standard one, that will be taken from now on.

The results (62)–(63), like the matching of any pairs of expansions which hold in overlapping domains, was carried out by implementing the following directive: “Equate the two reduced forms, each consisting of the approximate expansion for one domain from which the errors involved in the development of the other are weeded out.” Underlying this directive is the following rationale. The two reduced forms are comparable, because both deviate from the exact solutions, which is assumed to be unique, by the union of the two sets of errors. However, there is more than one way to identify the every same sets of the errors and thus implements that directive. In the foregoing derivation, the errors in the outlying the central region respectively, were defined:

of $0(\exp(-|\hat{\xi}|/\varepsilon))$ and of $0((\xi'\varepsilon')^i(\eta'\varepsilon')^j)$ where ε and ε' become vanishingly small while $(\hat{\xi}, \eta)$ as well as (ξ, η') are of $0(1)$. Yet, as shown below, the very same terms are suppressed if the errors are defined: of $0(\exp(-|\xi|))$ for large $|\xi|$ in the outlying solutions and or $0(\xi^i \eta^j)$ for small (ξ, η) in that prevailing close to the origin.

Indeed as (ξ, η) are increased, the components of the form (57) become large while the errors in the expansions for the outlying regions, which are of $0(\exp(-|\xi|))$, decay. Hence, adhering to the quoted directive, none of these components are weeded out in the reduction. Next, (ξ, η) are taken to be small and the solutions for the outlying regions are expanded as infinite series of terms of the type $\xi^i \eta^j$, where (i, j) equal $(0,0)$ $(1,0)$ $(0,1)$ and $(1,1)$, are anyway identical. Requiring that the terms of $0(\xi^0 \eta^2)$ should be equal, for each of the two pairs of matched expanded, one recovers the results (62)–(63).

All that is left is to match the free surface geometry and the pressure. Again the expansions representing these variables in the central region remain intact under the reduction spelled out in the directive in the quotes. On the other hand, for small (ξ, η) the expansions for the outlying regions become series of power of the type $\xi^i \eta^j$ for the pressure, and of the type x^i for the free surface variable. Matching only the terms of the $0(\xi^0 \eta^0)$ in the reduced expressions for the former and up to terms of $0(\xi^1)$ in those for the latter one gets

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{2a} \right) P_m = - \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) - \left(\frac{2B}{a^2} \right) t^2 \quad (64)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{2a} \right) P_m = \left(\frac{4M}{\pi} \right) \left(\frac{\pi}{2a} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{2a}{\pi} \right) \beta \quad (65)$$

$$e_0 = \beta \quad (66)$$

$$\beta = \hat{E} \quad (67)$$

$$e_1 = 1 - \beta \quad (68)$$

$$1 - \beta = \hat{E} t \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) \quad (69)$$

6 Summary

The considerations underlying the choice of there free constants, and hence also the errors involved in each regional solutions, will now be explained. The solutions for the two outlying regions are defined in terms of a and two

or else three additional free constants. This has been explained in the course of the construction of the solution for the tub. The solution for the layer is taken to be defined in terms of a, \hat{E} and t , while the constants \hat{B} and \hat{C} are linked to a, \hat{E} , and t via relationship (43)–(44). Then, as explained the solution for the central region, is defined in terms of four free constants e_0, e_1, P_m , and K . More are needed in order to represent this solution because it is matched with the other two while each of the latter two are matched with only one other. (In fact, four are insufficient if the meniscus effect is to be fully accounted for). The system of algebraic equations consisting of (62)–(69), the third of the set (54) together with (46) is, of course, determinant.

The physical considerations underlying this choice of free constants hinge on the direct correlations between the matching and the continuity of the variables that are being matched. Therefore all three dependent variables, which are of significance from fluid mechanic's viewpoint, are matched and are thus made—to some degree—continuous. The free surface is continuous and has a continuous slope. Moreover, the pressure is continuous and so ψ as well as all its ξ and η first and second derivations, except $\partial^2 \psi / \partial \xi^2$. It therefore follows that the velocity field is continuous and the stress field almost so. Note that it was thought advisable to sacrifice the continuity of $\partial^2 \psi / \partial \xi^2$ rather than that of $\partial^2 \psi / \partial \eta^2$. For, as explained the η variations are, on the whole, larger. Consequently, an error committed by letting $\partial \psi / \partial \eta^2$ be discontinuous would have had a bigger impact.

FIGURE 3. The comparison of the results for the current work with experimental findings of Spiers, Subbaraman, and Wilkinson (1974). The brown line depicts the current work.

7 Discussion

The values of the a as determined by equation (46) and (54) and (64)–(67), as well those obtained experimentally

by Spiers, Subbaraman and Wilkinson (1974) are plotted in fig. 3. The later latter were chosen as the basis for comparison because they cover the widest range of capillary number, T . Anyway all sets of the experimental results reported to data appear to have the same trend. The small quantitative differences between them are immaterial to the comparison brought herewith.

Evidently the experimental and computed findings are in good agreement so long as T is not too large. For vanishingly small T the experimental data fall almost right on the continuous v vs T curve computed. Note also that the set of experiments representing this dependence has a kink at some point in the range $1 > T > 0.1$ and this typifies not only the results of the work cited but those of most of the sets of experiments recorded to date. In the very same region, the calculated curve also brings to bend, though rather smoothly.

The inapplicability of the analysis proposed to high capillary number flows is believed to be related to the nature of the solution for the central region. The latter represents a free surface which is continuous and has continuous slope. However, unlike the other the other regional solutions it does not account for the influence of surface tension due to the curvature of the free surface. This is of little or no consequence when T is small. But in order to account for surface tension effect when it is large one would have to calculate many more terms in expansions (57), (58), and (59). Alternately, and this probably better, one could develop two expansions for that region: one around the origin and another around $(0, \pi/2)$.

This shortcoming should be weighed against the following three achievements attained here. Firstly, the mechanism underlying the tapering of the vertical layer was accounted for. Secondly, a coherent and comprehensive representation of the entire flow as was provided. Thirdly, the somewhat unfamiliar version of the method of the matched asymptotic expansion was “taken off the shelf”, where it had been lying unnoticed. Its merits were then demonstrated in its application to case at hand.

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Concluding Remarks

This article was in a process to be published about 1986 while the second author was a master student in Tel Aviv University. Professor Bentwich asked the second author to check some calculations in the paper. Bentwich passed away prematurely. Since then even the other inspiring individual of this work (see Acknowledgment) Professor Ernest Oliver (Ernie) Tuck also had passed away. The material moved from one place to another with the second author and finally is brought to life. All the mistakes and typos are responsibility of the second author. The ideas should be attributed to Professor Micheal Bentwich. The second author is only a poor conduit to pass these ideas from the past. During the past time, some of the notes have been lost and had to be reconstructed and thus introduced further errors. If you find an error please pass it to the second author so they could be corrected. There are other papers by Bentwich (as the main author) which are in a process bringing them to print (at this stage very much unlikely to written as it is very hard work to over this kind of material and lack of free time). These areas are more of mathematical rather than the natural area of the second author and hence they would not be not as good as they should be if Bentwich was able to finish them. Please note, the remarks like “Indeed” and “obviously” are sarcastic and they are the way Bentwich like joke (there normally are several pages to prove it.) and left for his memory. Because of that, this paper should be viewed more as a proof of concept for stitching asymptotic solutions.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he have NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers’ bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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